

Diagnostic Challenges of Leprosy in Primary Health Care: A Brazilian Case Report

Rafaela Castellar Corte (<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7953-5580>) rafaccorte@gmail.com;
Thiago Paes de Barros De Luccia (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5337-196X>)
tpbl78@gmail.com; Raquel Keller (<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0808-1896>)
raquelkellerdermatologista@gmail.com.

São Leopoldo Mandic Araras College

Introduction

Leprosy is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. Although its clinical course is typically slow and insidious, the disease carries a substantial risk of physical disability and permanent neurological impairment when diagnosis and treatment are delayed (Beiguelman, 2002). Transmission occurs primarily through prolonged exposure to respiratory secretions from untreated individuals with multibacillary disease (Beiguelman, 2002). Recognized risk factors include residence in endemic areas, adverse socioeconomic conditions, genetic susceptibility, and close household contact with patients affected by multibacillary leprosy (Beiguelman, 2002).

Despite the availability of effective treatment, delayed diagnosis remains a major challenge in endemic countries, contributing both to ongoing transmission and to the development of preventable disabilities (Jesus et al., 2023). Brazil reports the second-highest number of leprosy cases worldwide and remains a priority country for disease control and elimination efforts (Jesus et al., 2023).

The persistence of diagnostic delays highlights the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for leprosy within Primary Health Care (PHC), particularly among Family Health teams. This report describes the case of a patient whose diagnosis was established five months after symptom onset, during which multiple alternative diagnostic hypotheses were considered. The case illustrates the challenges associated with recognizing leprosy in PHC settings and emphasizes the critical role of longitudinal care and care coordination in achieving a timely diagnosis.

According to Starfield, PHC is founded on four essential attributes: first-contact access, longitudinality, comprehensiveness, and care coordination, complemented by family and community orientation (Starfield, 2002). In the present case, diagnostic delay was associated with low initial clinical suspicion, resulting in non-directed clinical assessments and the absence of a comprehensive dermatoneurological examination during the first consultations. Conversely, the longitudinal nature of PHC enabled repeated patient evaluations and the development of a therapeutic relationship, facilitating diagnostic reconsideration over time. Care coordination also played a pivotal role by enabling appropriate referrals and integration of specialist assessments, ultimately ensuring comprehensive management.

This case demonstrates how the core attributes of PHC can contribute both to the identification of diagnostic gaps and to their eventual resolution. The report aims to analyze the diagnostic challenges of leprosy in Primary Health Care through the presentation of a real-world case involving a five-month diagnostic delay. Furthermore, it highlights how low initial clinical suspicion and fragmented assessment may hinder early disease recognition, while emphasizing the importance of dermatoneurological examination, effective care coordination, and ongoing professional training of Family Health teams for timely diagnosis, disability prevention, and interruption of disease transmission.

Case Report

The patient provided written informed consent authorizing the use of clinical data for academic and scientific purposes. The study was approved by the local Research Ethics Committee (Plataforma Brasil - CAAE: 8681212500005374).

November 11, 2024. A 37-year-old male patient, born and residing in the western region of São Paulo State, Brazil, presented to a Primary Health Care unit complaining of pain and increased local temperature in the right knee for approximately one week. His past medical history was significant for heart failure with a left ventricular ejection fraction of 38% of unknown etiology. He reported smoking three cigarettes daily since childhood and was regularly taking spironolactone, simvastatin, and omeprazole.

The patient had previously been referred to an orthopedic specialist because of significant low back pain. Physical examination revealed mild erythema and edema of the right knee (Figure 1), as well as an approximately 1.5-cm area of induration in the popliteal region.

The initial diagnostic hypotheses included erysipelas and superficial thrombophlebitis. Laboratory investigations were requested, including a complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP), and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR). Empirical treatment with cephalexin was initiated, and the patient was referred for vascular surgery evaluation.

November 21, 2024. At follow-up, erythema and edema persisted, with apparent extension toward the proximal tibial region. Laboratory results obtained on November 12, 2024, showed hemoglobin 15.1 g/dL, hematocrit 47.7%, leukocyte count 6,300/mm³ without abnormalities, platelet count 218,000/mm³, CRP 0.5 mg/dL, and ESR 3 mm/h. The patient reported having sought care at an Emergency Care Unit, from which he was referred to a tertiary hospital. Ciprofloxacin and clindamycin had been prescribed, and hospitalization was recommended; however, the patient declined admission.

January 27, 2025. The patient reported having attended consultations with vascular surgery and orthopedics, and a knee radiograph had been requested. During orthopedic evaluation, knee arthrocentesis was performed, yielding hemorrhagic synovial fluid. Vascular assessment ruled out circulatory abnormalities. The patient reported having used amoxicillin-clavulanate. During this consultation, he first reported hypoesthesia over the patellar region of the right knee. He was subsequently referred for dermatological evaluation.

February 3, 2025. During dermatological assessment, the patient reported progressive worsening of the condition, with enlargement of pre-existing lesions and the appearance of new lesions.

Dermatological examination revealed erythematous-violaceous, shiny, infiltrated plaques distributed over the right lower limb. The right knee showed marked edema, increased local temperature, and pain on examination, consistent with inflammatory arthritis. Careful skin examination demonstrated focal areas of desquamation, suggestive of a recent inflammatory episode.

Several lesions exhibited central hypopigmentation with relative clearing, surrounded by well-defined inner margins and poorly demarcated outer borders extending into adjacent normal skin. This morphological pattern corresponded to so-called "foveolar lesions" or a "Swiss cheese" appearance, a characteristic finding in borderline leprosy (Figures 2A–C).

Based on these clinical findings—including the presence of foveolar lesions, progression of existing lesions, emergence of new lesions, areas of desquamation, arthritis, and altered cutaneous sensation surrounded by areas of preserved sensitivity—a diagnosis of Type 1 leprosy reaction (reversal reaction) in a patient with borderline leprosy was suspected. The patient was referred to a specialized leprosy reference center, where the diagnosis of borderline leprosy with Type 1 reaction was clinically confirmed by experienced dermatologists and multidrug therapy was initiated.

At the referral center, five samples were collected for slit-skin smear bacilloscopy and complementary investigations. Laboratory tests performed on February 12, 2025, showed fasting glucose 65 mg/dL, creatinine 1.01 mg/dL, aspartate aminotransferase (AST) 19 U/L, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) 15 U/L, gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) 40 U/L, total cholesterol 238 mg/dL, triglycerides 103 mg/dL, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) 9.4 U/g Hb (within normal limits), activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) 35.6 seconds, hemoglobin 15.5 g/dL, hematocrit 47.7%, leukocyte count 4,740/mm³, and platelet count 224,000/mm³.

Multibacillary multidrug therapy (MB-MDT) was initiated with supervised administration of rifampicin 600 mg, clofazimine 300 mg, and dapsone 100 mg.

February 27, 2025. During a home visit, the patient was found at home with his wife. He reported partial recovery of sensation in the affected knee region. He was receiving self-administered daily doses of dapsone 100 mg and clofazimine 50 mg. No household contacts reported skin lesions suggestive of leprosy.

Results of slit-skin smear bacilloscopy performed on February 6, 2025 (one sample from a skin lesion, two from the right earlobe, and two from the right elbow), revealed rare acid-fast bacilli in only one specimen obtained from the right elbow, corresponding to 1–10 bacilli per 100 microscopic fields examined. The referral service recommended contact screening for all household members.

April 10, 2025. During follow-up at the Primary Health Care unit, the patient was questioned regarding the use of corticosteroids for management of the reversal reaction but was unable to provide this information. He continued to report intermittent swelling of the affected lower limb and persistent knee pain. Physical examination demonstrated mild hyperpigmentation and partial regression of the previously described erythematous-violaceous plaques (Figures 3A–C).

Discussion

This case illustrates the diagnostic challenges posed by leprosy in Primary Health Care (PHC), particularly when the initial presentation is dominated by atypical manifestations. The patient's therapeutic itinerary, characterized by multiple consultations across different specialties—including orthopedics, vascular surgery, and emergency services—before a definitive diagnosis was established, reflects a pattern frequently described in endemic settings and highlights the consequences of low initial clinical suspicion (Martins and Iriart, 2014). The five-month delay between symptom onset and initiation of multidrug therapy is clinically relevant, as delayed diagnosis is associated with an increased risk of irreversible neurological impairment and continued transmission within the community (Costa et al., 2017).

The initial presentation, consisting primarily of knee pain, localized inflammation, and arthritis, directed clinical reasoning toward more common diagnoses such as erysipelas, thrombophlebitis, and musculoskeletal disorders. This scenario underscores the well-recognized clinical polymorphism of leprosy and reinforces the importance of considering the disease in the differential diagnosis of chronic inflammatory, dermatological, and neurological conditions in endemic regions (Froes et al., 2022). Notably, sensory impairment—a cardinal sign of leprosy—was recognized only several months after the first consultation. This finding highlights the critical importance of performing a systematic dermatoneurological examination in all patients presenting with unexplained skin lesions or peripheral neuropathic symptoms (Brazil, 2022a).

An important aspect of the present case is the apparent discrepancy between the strong clinical suspicion of borderline leprosy with Type 1 reaction and the nearly negative slit-skin smear results. Only one specimen demonstrated rare acid-fast bacilli, a finding that could potentially raise questions regarding diagnostic certainty. However, leprosy remains fundamentally a clinical diagnosis, particularly in borderline forms, in which bacillary burden may be low and bacteriological confirmation is not always achieved.

In this case, the diagnosis was clinically confirmed by dermatologists at a specialized leprosy referral center based on characteristic findings, including infiltrated plaques with a foveolar (“Swiss cheese”) appearance, sensory impairment within affected lesions, progression of pre-existing lesions, emergence of new lesions, inflammatory arthritis, and clinical features consistent with a Type 1 (reversal) reaction. Although slit-skin smear bacilloscopy revealed only rare bacilli, the combination of characteristic dermatological and neurological findings, concordant specialist evaluation, exclusion of alternative diagnoses during the diagnostic

workup, and subsequent clinical improvement following multidrug therapy strongly support the diagnosis of borderline leprosy. Furthermore, the recovery of sensation and partial regression of skin lesions observed after treatment initiation provide additional evidence supporting the diagnostic hypothesis and are consistent with an appropriate therapeutic response. This case highlights the limitations of relying solely on bacteriological findings and reinforces the importance of comprehensive clinical assessment in endemic settings.

The occurrence of a Type 1 (reversal) reaction contributed substantially to the diagnostic complexity. Reversal reactions are delayed-type (Type IV) hypersensitivity responses directed against *Mycobacterium leprae* antigens and represent one of the most common immunological complications in borderline forms of the disease (Costa et al., 2017). Clinically, they are characterized by acute inflammation of existing lesions, appearance of new lesions, neuritis, and, in some cases, systemic manifestations. Although the skin and peripheral nerves are the primary targets, musculoskeletal involvement may occur and can manifest as arthritis, as observed in the present case (Goulart et al., 2002). Such manifestations may divert attention from the underlying diagnosis and contribute to delays in recognition.

The patient's recovery of sensation following treatment initiation suggests that the disease was identified before the development of permanent neural damage. This favorable outcome reinforces the importance of early recognition and prompt treatment of both leprosy and reactional episodes. Corticosteroid therapy remains the cornerstone of management for reversal reactions because it reduces inflammatory nerve injury and prevents long-term disability (Costa et al., 2017).

The diagnostic delay observed in this case is consistent with findings from previous studies evaluating the therapeutic itinerary of individuals affected by leprosy. Repeated consultations, multiple referrals, and empirical treatments before diagnostic confirmation are frequently reported in endemic areas and reflect persistent difficulties in recognizing early manifestations of the disease (Martins and Iriart, 2014). In some studies, diagnostic delays have ranged from a few months to several years, with mean intervals exceeding two years (Martins and Iriart, 2014).

From a health systems perspective, this case highlights the central role of PHC in the management of leprosy. The Brazilian Clinical Protocol and Therapeutic Guidelines for Leprosy recommend that diagnosis, treatment, follow-up, and contact surveillance be integrated into PHC whenever possible, thereby ensuring continuity of care and comprehensive management (Brazil, 2022b). In the present case, although several specialists were involved, the longitudinal relationship established with the PHC team enabled repeated reassessments and ultimately facilitated diagnostic clarification.

Care coordination was another key element. The ability of the PHC team to integrate information obtained from different levels of care and maintain continuous follow-up contributed significantly to the eventual diagnosis and treatment adherence. Likewise, home visits played an important role by allowing assessment of household contacts and reinforcing

surveillance measures aimed at early case detection. These actions exemplify the attributes of longitudinality and care coordination proposed by Starfield and demonstrate their practical relevance in the management of complex conditions such as leprosy.

Finally, this case aligns with the objectives of Brazil's National Strategy for Leprosy Control 2024–2030 (Brazil, 2024), which emphasizes strengthening surveillance, expanding access to timely diagnosis, reducing disability, promoting social inclusion, and combating stigma associated with the disease. The persistence of diagnostic delays, even in endemic regions, demonstrates the continued need for professional training and heightened awareness among Primary Health Care teams. Greater recognition of atypical presentations, routine performance of dermatoneurological examinations, and effective coordination between primary and specialized care may substantially improve early detection and reduce the burden of leprosy-related disability.

Conclusion

This case highlights the diagnostic complexity of leprosy when atypical manifestations predominate and classic neurological findings are not initially recognized. Delayed diagnosis resulted from low initial clinical suspicion and the absence of a systematic dermatoneurological examination, leading to multiple consultations and alternative diagnostic hypotheses before definitive recognition of the disease. The case also demonstrates that borderline leprosy with Type 1 reaction may present with prominent inflammatory and musculoskeletal manifestations, potentially mimicking more common conditions encountered in Primary Health Care.

The favorable clinical response following multidrug therapy, together with the characteristic dermatological and neurological findings and specialist confirmation at a referral center, supported the diagnosis despite minimally positive bacilloscopic findings. Ultimately, this report reinforces the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for leprosy in endemic settings and highlights the essential role of longitudinal care, care coordination, contact surveillance, and comprehensive dermatoneurological assessment in achieving timely diagnosis, preventing disability, and reducing disease transmission.

Figure 1. Right knee showing mild erythema and edema at the initial presentation. Photograph obtained on November 11, 2024.

Figure 2. Clinical presentation of the right knee during dermatological evaluation. (A) Medial aspect showing an infiltrated erythematous plaque with central hypopigmentation and relatively well-defined inner borders. (B) Lateral aspect demonstrating a similar plaque morphology. (C) Lateral aspect showing marked edema associated with the lesion.

Figure 3. Follow-up clinical photographs of the right knee after initiation of multidrug therapy. (A) Medial aspect. (B) Lateral aspect. (C) Lateral aspect demonstrating partial regression of inflammation and residual hyperpigmentation of the lesions.

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